

Several equivalent formulas of ionization energy of hydrogen atom

HuangShan

(Wuhu Institute of Technology, China, Wuhu, 241003)

Abstract: Several equivalent formulas of ionization energy of hydrogen atom.

Key words: Planck constant, universal Gravitational constant formula, Coulomb's law.

Why is the ratio of Planck constant to reduced Planck constant 2π ? There is an inverse operation, $\frac{h}{\hbar} = 2\pi$, $\Leftrightarrow \frac{(e_0)(\mu_0)}{(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)(a_0)} = 2\pi$, $\Leftrightarrow \frac{(e_0)(\mu_0)}{4\pi} = \frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)(a_0)$, $\Leftrightarrow (e_0)(\mu_0)(R_\infty) = \frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0]$. In the "standard" physical formula, with regard to the ionization energy of hydrogen atoms, there are $\frac{h(c)(R_\infty)}{(e_0)} = \frac{(1312000)(1000)(m_{atom})}{(e_0)} = 13.6 \text{ eV}$.

Then, according to the "numerical guess formula" above, there can be $\frac{h(c)(R_\infty)}{(e_0)} = \frac{(13120000)(1000)(m_{atom})}{(e_0)} = (\mu_0)(R_\infty) = (k_B)(c)^2(R_\infty) = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0]}{(e_0)} = 13.6 \text{ eV}$. And because of two formulas about distance, $(E_m) = \frac{(q_m)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)2\pi(a_0)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_m)(h)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_m)(G_N)}{(r)^2}$, $(E_e) = \frac{(q_e)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_e)(c)(a_0)}{(e_0)(R_\infty)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_e)(k)}{(r)^2}$, so, $(m_e)(R_\infty)^2(c)(G_N) = \frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)^2(\mu_0)(k)}{(c)(a_0)} = \frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0]$.

So, does the ionization energy of other atoms also mean that the ionization energy is related to the Rydberg constant and permeability, or it can be converted by its electron orbital velocity?

There's an inverse operation about the basic atom, $(m_{atom})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2 = \frac{(\mu_0)(e_0)}{(a_0)(c)}$, $\Leftrightarrow (m_e) = \frac{(\mu_0)(e_0)}{2\pi(a_0)(c)[\alpha_0](c)}$, $(m_{atom})(c)^4 = 2\pi[\alpha_0](c)$, $\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0](c) = \frac{(e_0)[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)}$. Then contact the above formula about the ionization energy of the hydrogen atom, so several equivalent formulas of the ionization energy of the hydrogen atom are $(h)(c)(R_\infty) = (e_0)(\mu_0)(R_\infty) = (e_0)(k_B)(c)^2(R_\infty) = (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(c)(G_N) = \frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)^2(\mu_0)(k)}{(c)(a_0)} = \frac{(e_0)[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)} = \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0](c)$, Then, $\frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)^2(\mu_0)(k)}{(c)(a_0)} = \frac{(e_0)[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)}$, $\Leftrightarrow \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)(k)}{(a_0)} = (c)$, $\frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = \frac{h}{(a_0)} = (m_{atom})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2$, $\Leftrightarrow \frac{(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)(c)^2(c)} = (m_{atom})$, $\frac{(m_{atom})(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^2(m_{atom})(c)^2}{(m_e)}$.

So why is the electron escape velocity of the hydrogen atom equal to the encircling velocity? So, can we assume that the derivation of the ionization energy of the hydrogen atom is equivalent to the basic unit operation in the definition domain of some mathematical formulas, but the electron is not in this definition domain?

Where (ϵ_0) is the Vacuum dielectric constant, (μ_0) is the Permeability of vacuum, (c) is the Speed of light, (e_0) is the Elementary charge, $[\alpha_0]$ is the Fine structure constant, (R_∞) is the Rydberg constant, (a_0) is the Bohr radius, (m_{atom}) is the Basic atomic mass, (m_e) is the Electron rest mass, (h) is the Reduced Planck constant, $(\hbar)$ is the Planck constant. (k_B) is the Boltzmann constant, (k) is the Electrostatic force constant, (G_N) is the Gravitational constant.

Reference: none.